

Small e/T Limit For Probability Distributions and a Link to the MB Distribution

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In previous notes, we pointed out that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions become the MB (Maxwell-Boltzmann) distribution in the $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ limit. The key idea of the MB distribution seems to be: $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ ((1)) if $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. This distribution (and others) are strongly based on conservation of energy in collisions/interactions, namely $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. This conservation of energy equation may be immediately obtained by using either a power law b power i in ((1)), or the linear form $a + be_i$. The point, we argue, is that the latter is the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit of any distribution $p(e_i)$ which is not singular at $e_i/T = 0$ and has a nonvanishing first derivative at this point. In other words, the MB distribution is to be expected in the low e_i/T limit not only for the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions, but for many others and seems to show the importance of conservation of energy and the e_i as information in the low e_i/T limit. Basically, it seems that in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, $p(e_i)$ loses any information except that of e_i/T (and the $1 - e_i/T$ ensures a product law becomes addition. Thus, one cannot even distinguish between the form of the function because all higher terms have been lost. Now, $a + be_i/T = a(1 + be_i/(Ta))$ and so this immediately approximates a $\exp(be_i/aT)$. This is the MB distribution in the case of $b/a = -1$, but always satisfies ((1)). In the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases, one obtains the exact MB result.

Tsallis and Kaniadakis Cases

If one argues for a probability distribution which behaves as a power law for $e_i/T \gg 1$, then one essentially has a linear e_i/T to a negative power. The problem is that for $e_i/T = 0$, one has a singularity. This, however, may be easily removed by considering:

$(a + e_i/T)$ power negative number ((2)) a is a finite number

For e_i/T almost 0, one may write $a(1 + e_i/Ta)$ power negative number ((3)). If $1/a = \text{absolute value of the negative number}$, then one obtains the exact MB distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

((2)) only holds in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit and so the full distribution may be something different as is the case. One may note, however, that for $e_i/T \gg 1$, a essentially drops out and one obtains a dropping power law. Furthermore, if one wishes have a linear e_i/T in () for $e_i/T \gg 1$, then any:

$(a_1 + b_1 e_i/T + \dots + b_n e_i/T \text{ power } n)$ power $1/n$ ((4))

polynomial replacing a in ((2)) will suffice, but for $e_i/T \ll 1$, one requires ((1)) which means that one needs to have terms which represent an expansion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for e_i/T . This restricts the polynomial in ((4)) to:

$(a_1 + b_1 e_i/T + b_2 e_i^2/T^2)$ power $1/2$ replacing a in ((2)).

The problem is that ((2)) does not really represent a power law drop for $e_i/T \gg 1$ and so it would be better to set $b_1=0$, which then leads to the Kaniadakis distribution.

The above arguments seem qualitative at best and so we try to see if there is a more general idea at work which goes beyond the Tsallis and Kaniadakis formalisms.

Small e_i/T Limit for any Probability Distribution

The basis idea of the MB distribution is ((1))

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ for } e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l \text{ leading to } \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ ((5))}$$

A power law satisfies ((5)) for any e_i/T , but if one considers $e_i/T \ll 1$, then a linear function:

$$a+be_i/T \text{ ((6)) also satisfies ((1)) up to first order in } e_i/T.$$

In such a case, a and b follow from a Taylor expansion of any probability function which is not singular at the origin and has a nonvanishing first derivative. As a result, in such a limit, any such probability distribution behaves in a mathematical manner like an MB distribution. In the case of $a=1$ and $b=1$, one obtains the exact MB result. In other words, for $e_i/T \ll 1$, one may write:

$$a+be_i/T = a(1+be_i/Ta) \text{ and call } b/Ta = -T_1, \text{ i.e. a new temperature so to speak ((6))}$$

In such a case, all probability distributions (nonsingular and with a nonvanishing first derivative at $e_i/T=0$) behave in an MB fashion in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit. What this seems to imply is that information about the functional form of the distribution is basically lost for $e_i/T \ll 1$ (only a piece is left in the value of T_1) and one essentially has the limit of $\exp(-e_i/T_1)$.

Basically, for $e_i/T \ll 1$, all $p(e_i)$ values are so close, that they are only distinguished by tiny e_i/T differences from the same constant. Thus, a product of any two $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ can only yield the constant and changes e_i, e_j as a sum and given that conservation of e is key physically, one must, by conservation of energy have: $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ to first order for $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$. Thus, in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, one seems to have an information problem restricted by conservation of e_i 's.

Practical Consequences

If one considers the Tsallis distribution:

$$p(e_i) = (1+(1-q)(-e_i/T))^{-1/(1-q)} \text{ unnormalized ((7))}$$

then it is well-known that it becomes $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for $q=1$. We are, however, interested in the case of $q \neq 1$. Is there then any link to the MB case? We argue that there is in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit. The distribution ((7)) becomes an exact MB distribution in both the $q=1$ case and the e_i/T limit, i.e. $T_1=T$.

Why should this be the case? If one considers:

$\ln q(p) = -e_i/T$ (for all e_i) = $(1 - p)^{1-q} / (1-q)$ and uses $p = (a + be_i/T)^{1/(1-q)}$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$, then:

Then: $a=1$ and $b=-1+q$ so $p = (1 + (1-q)(-e_i/T))^{1/(1-q)}$ which may be converted to an exp form and then back to $1 - e_i/T$, i.e the exact MB form regardless of the value of q .

The exact result holds for the Kaniadakis case because for $e_i/T \ll 1$, $\sqrt[1+q]{1 + ke_i/T}$ approx = 1.

Thus, we argue that the MB case is hidden in the e_i/T limit of both of these distributions and in many others (even if one may need to adjust the value of T).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is based on $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j)$ ((1)), i.e $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$, but in the low e_i/T limit this becomes $1 - e_i/T$. The point we make is that any probability distribution which is not singular at $e_i/T=0$ and has a nonvanishing first derivative at this point has a Talyor series expansion to first order of $a + be_i/T$ which satisfies to first order the condition ((1)) and hence mimics a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in this limit even if it may be with a different T value.